

HISTORY OF HISTORICAL-CULTURAL MONUMENTS OF KAKOND CITY

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Abstract: the article discusses the history of historical and cultural monuments of the city of Kokand, which were built in the XVIII and early XX centuries and are still preserved without losing their historical significance.

Key words: "The Golden People of Fergana", Davan, "Khoqand", "Havoqand", "Khulasa al-Tawarikh", Dahmaishahon's mausoleum, Kamalqazi

The city of Kokan is the last big city in Fergana region along the route of "Fergana Golden Nation". It is located in the western part of the Fergana Valley, at the foot of the Sokh River, at an altitude of 450 m above sea level, and has a population of 180,000 people. In ancient Chinese written sources dating back to the II-I centuries BC, the state of Davan, located in the Ferghana Valley, is mentioned several times. At that time, the capital of the Davan state was the city of Ershi, and some researchers believe that it was in the place of today's Kokan. However, this hypothesis is not confirmed by archaeological data. Maybe there really were cities or villages here in ancient times, but Kokan was first mentioned in the written sources of Arab geographers in the 10th century. When describing the main road leading from Khojand to Osh, the Arab traveler geographer Istakhri mentions the city of Kokand, "one big pass from Sokh and 5 farsakhs from Syrdarya" on this road. Another Arab traveler Ibn Khawqal describes the city as very beautiful and calls it "Khoqand" or "Havoqand". Yakut Hamavi and Muhammad Taqi also mentioned the city of "Havoqand" in their geographical works (XIII century). In the 13th century, the city was destroyed by the Mongols, and it was completely restored only at the beginning of the 18th century. It is true that Mahmud Hakim Yaifani in his work "Khulasa al-Tawarikh" (XIV century) states that the king stopped in "Khoqand" during Babur's retreat to Samarkand under the pressure of the Shaibanis. Babur himself mentions "Khoqand" in "Boburnoma". 24 V.P. Nalivkin's work "Brief history of the Kokhan Khanate" reports that the city was originally called "Old fortress" or "Rahimbii fortress" and was founded in 1732, based on the information of local historians. In the place of the city, there were four fortresses - Kalvak, Oktepa, Eski kurgan and Khakan kurgan. 1740 is considered the year of reconstruction of the city of Kokan, which was destroyed by the Mongols in the 13th century. At the beginning of the 18th century, the Kokan Khanate developed in the Fergana Valley, and the city of Kokan became its capital. Crafts and trade developed in the city, and cultural life revived. Cotton and cocoon growing is developed in the Kokan area. In 1830, the city occupied a large area, with 6 markets and 3000 houses. In 1842, the khanate fought with Bukhara for Khojand, and then, when the uprising of the people against the viceroy of Bukhara began, the new khan of Kokand, Sherali Khan, built a defensive wall. In the 19th century, there were 6 bathhouses, 9 caravanserais, 3,000 yards and 30,000

inhabitants in Kokan. Arminy Vamberi, who was in Khiva and Bukhara in the 19th century, based on the information of some authors, wrote that Kokan is 6 times bigger than Khiva, 2 times bigger than Bukhara and 4 times bigger than Tehran. Before the Kokan Khanate became a Russian colony, the city had 10,000 courtyards, 300 mosques, 120 schools, 40 madrasahs and 2,000 stalls. Kokan was a model feudal city with an area of 160 by 5 miles surrounded by thick walls. The city is divided into 12 administrative parts - Khojand, Ghaziyogliq, Kuduklik, Sarimazar, Namangan, Chimion, Sokh, Margilan, Rishton, Muymuborak, Qatagon and Isfara, each of them had its own gate. The city was mainly supplied with water by the Aksuv (Sokh) river, which stretches for a distance of 35 kilometers. Navbahor, Qataghon, Ganjirvan, Kichiksoy and Kattasoy streams, which go from the river to the city, merge in the northeast and flow into the Syrdarya. Most of the streams have survived to our days. There was a big market in the center of the city. In the Fergana Valley, at the beginning of the 20th century, the Kokan market stood out, second only to the Bukhara market in terms of size and trade turnover. Four main roads led to the center of the shopping area. It was surrounded by mosques, including a 20-jame mosque with a tall brick minaret. These four main roads divided the city into four parts. Single-story houses with flat roofs are set within landscaped courtyards behind tall thatched walls. Mosques with high pediments and minarets were much higher than residential areas, and most of them have not been preserved to us. A fort was built by Khudoyor Khan in the northwestern part of the city. In the middle of the 19th century, the city covered all the lands along the Syrdarya River. Sometimes it included the lands of Tashkent region, Jizzakh, Khojand and Samarkand, for which there was a regular struggle with the Bukhara Emirate. After the establishment of the Fergana governorate and its incorporation into the general governorate of Turkestan, the city of Koqan remained the central city and was given the right of independent management. Even when the regional center was officially moved to New Margilon in 1877, Kokan was still managed by the head of the uezd, who controlled the entire administrative system. 25 In the 19th century, Kokan became one of the largest handicraft centers. There were 276 silk factories, 428 cotton factories, 67 tanneries, 1312 private factories, 599 state factories, etc. in the city. In 1878, at the agricultural exhibition in Tashkent, Kokan craftsmen exhibited silk, knitted, paper dyed products and musical instruments. The products were also exhibited at exhibitions in Moscow, Novgorod and Paris. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, Kokan supported intensive relations with a number of foreign countries. In 1882, it was in the first place in the export of goods to the cities of the Russian Empire. Offices and societies of Russian trade firms, industrialists appeared in the city. In 1890-1894, 8 banks were established in Kokan. Kokand conducted intensive trade with Iran, India, Afghanistan and other countries using ancient caravan routes. Kokan merchants, together with the Moscow firm, conducted trade with Kashgar through the Great Silk Road. Goods from the Russian state and other western countries passed through Kokan to eastern countries. In 1913, a list of imported goods worth 1,117,198 rubles was registered at the Kokan customs house. It was mainly tea, glass, electrical appliances, knitwear, handicrafts, etc. In the same year, 3,004,284 rubles worth of sugar, matches, tobacco, silk products, etc. were exported. The role of the market in trade was certainly incomparable. Existing markets in the city acted as an intermediary in the purchase of local raw materials. Caravanserai also played a big role in domestic trade, and in 1919 there were 44 of them. Almost no historical monuments have been preserved in the city. Among the most notable architectural monuments is the palace of

the last ruler, Khudoyor Khan, built in 1871. Currently, this palace functions as a local history museum. According to the architectural forms, the Khudoyar Khan palace does not differ much from the buildings created in the 19th century in Central Asia. However, the exterior of the palace has its own peculiarities. The combination of Mayo paints is not at all characteristic of the appearance of architectural monuments in the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. Almost all the colors of the rainbow were used in the outer covering of the Khudoyar Khan Palace. At first glance, this variety dazzles the eye, which is accustomed to the pale colors of other architectural monuments in Central Asia. However, the more one looks at the combination of pictures and colors, the more one is surprised by the originality of the pictures in the pattern and is sure that they are not repeated once in the 14 shelves that decorate the exterior of the building. The inner rooms of the palace are decorated with brightly colored plant-like patterns. The palace complex, which has survived to this day, is located on the outskirts of the city and is very well planned. The skill of the architects of the 19th century was reflected in the project structure and decoration methods. The name of the architect is also known - the construction was led by Mir Ubaidulla. Construction lasted from 1863 to 1870. The attractive decorations were made by famous craftsmen Abdulla and Jamil from Rishton, and master Zakir from Pskent. The colorful decorations on the ceiling of the palace and the carved alabaster decorations in the hall of the palace were made by masters named Fazilkhoja, Mamasidiq and Yoldosh Najarboshi. 26 The complex consisted of a series of walkable courtyards leading to the gate, representing a system of palaces and buildings running along an axis from West to East. Nearby there were rooms for guards and stables for guests' horses. All these are not preserved now. Formerly a magnificent palace with additional rooms, located on one axis and occupying the Western side, has been preserved. The palace of Khudoyar Khan is raised on a high platform, and a long and sloping path leads to its main doors. The facade of the building is distinguished from other similar buildings of the 19th century by the richness and brightness of the colors used. It consists of layers of baked bricks, surrounded by a square border, decorated with successive large and small lancet arches. The status of lancet arches is also observed in the decoration of the front side of the wall. At the entrance doors to the palace territory, the front arch, inserted into the central pediment, attracts attention. The high gable and the entire front of the palace are protected from the sides by delicate lanterns covered by glazed domes at the corners. From the front side of the palace, all the walls and corner towers are covered with composite mosaics, which form various panels and pattern decorations according to the picture. The front of the palace is decorated with a series of attractive sand dunes. The palace is a slightly elongated quadrangle in plan, and is divided into three parts, filled with inner courtyards surrounded by about one hundred and twenty rooms. In front of the courtyard was the main courtyard with a colonnade of tims adjacent to two halls for large and small receptions, and in front of these halls there were small waiting rooms. The second courtyard was connected to the northern part of this courtyard, where the mosque, treasury and divan were located. In the middle part of the palace are the rooms where the khan himself lived and farm buildings for the servants who serve the khan and his family. The rear part of the palace was occupied by three large courtyards consisting of a two-story building, where all the family members lived. From the north side, the yard is adjoined by a stable, buildings where soldiers live, and other buildings related to the service of the yard. On the south and west sides there were ponds and ponds. Since 1875, Russian troops have been stationed around the palace, and a new administration

has been stationed in the palace yard. Military fortifications and strengthened barracks were built instead of the courtyards leading to the palace gate. The palace also housed officers, family members of the administration, and the treasury, and the great throne room was converted into a church. Currently, only the front part of the old khan's palace, consisting of the throne hall, the column of timlar and the cabinet building, has been preserved. A museum of historical and local history is operating here. In the throne room, a glass railing overlooking the pool has been preserved. In 1877, Russian artists performed in the large hall of the Khan's palace, which could accommodate 170 people. The repertoire of the troupe includes songs such as "Innocent Sinless" by V. Aleksandrov, "Marriage", "Emperor Maximilian", "Not every cat has a holiday", "Generous" by N.V. Gogol. 27 In 1924, an agricultural exhibition was held in the former khan's palace. The exhibition materials served as the basis for the creation of a local history museum in the palace building. In 1925, the art department was opened in the museum. Thanks to the artists M.A. Arinin and N.F. Yakovlev, the capital museums in Moscow and Leningrad selected a number of exhibits, created a painting exposition, and opened a sculpture department. The museum has collected wonderful photos and documents about the city's history, attractions and famous people. The exhibition of folk masters is in progress. The historical monuments include the Norbotabi Madrasa, the ceiling of which is decorated with wonderful patterns, and the Mausoleum of Madiri Khan, the burial place of the women of the Khan family. The mausoleum of Dahmaishahon and the Kamalqazi mosque have been preserved, and their gate pediments are decorated with Mayo tiles in a geometric style. Among the cultural and educational institutions in the city of Kokan, the theater in the old city, which was inactive for a long time due to lack of funds and was restored in 1925, occupies an important place. Examples of Russian architecture from the 19th century, mainly bank buildings, have been preserved in the city. European-style buildings began to be built outside the castle in the 19th century. In 1908, a church was built in the South-Eastern direction. The military assembly and some state institutions are located in the same place. The city lost the status of the capital, and its buildings differed from the common constructions adopted in other cities. A linear project system was created and it was based on the systems of two streets - Rosenbach avenue, which runs along the southern side of the palace to the west, and Skobelev street, which leads to the station since 1891. Although Kokan was not an administrative center, at the end of the 19th century it quickly became a center of domestic and foreign trade. Local and foreign firms engaged in intermediary trade, especially in cotton and cocoons, as well as financial activities settled here. Therefore, the appearance of the new Kokan was different from other Asian cities. This was caused by the construction of luxury houses for a large number of banks, offices and private entrepreneurs. The commercial part of the city is located on the South-West side of the fortress in the city, and the Uchburchak society store was built, which differs from the other buildings with window frames and false Russian forms in the form of a tent. Alperovich's store, Galam designer store, Vilde pharmacy, two-story Bulle hotel with restaurant were built on Rosenbach Avenue, between the corner of Skobelev Street and the church, which enlivened this part of the street.

Currently, Kokan is one of the industrial centers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. There are more than 28 industrial enterprises in the city, including "Elektromash" and "Kokontektilmash" factories, a flour factory, an oil-oil factory, a superphosphate factory and others. A pedagogical institute, a branch of a polytechnic institute, 7 colleges, including oil, agricultural

mechanization, 28 communal farms, a mining combine and 14 vocational lyceums are operating in Kok. Scientists born and raised in the city of Kokand made a great contribution to the development of science and technology in our republic. Among them are academicians U. Arifov, T. Zohidov, M. Orazboev, S. Sirojiddinov, D. Saidov, M. Mukhamedjanov, M. Yuldashevlar, A. Aminov, H. Komilova, R. Aminova, M. Khairullaev, M. Rakhmanov, N. Abubakirov, honored representatives of science - M. Kariev, U. Tursunov, M. Musaev, A. Kayumov, M. Saidalieva and many others can be listed. Kokan is the homeland of Hamza Hakimzada Niyazi, Sabir Abdulla and Abdulla Qahhor. Also, Mukumi, Furqat, Zavqi, Charkhi (Askarali Khamroliev), A. Umari, Sh. The names of poets and writers such as Riza, T. Fattah, U. Nasir, H. Shams, I. Sadikov, S. Husain are also known to many. Popular artists such as Halima Nosirova and Nabi Rahimov were born in the city. Cinematography plays a big role in cultural education. There are 8 cinemas, 4 museums, sports facilities, music college, etc. operating in Kokan. Among the cultural and household objects, it is possible to mention the "Koqon" hotel located on Furqat Street. Its main decoration is the carved door of K. Khaidarov. National architectural styles were successfully used in the bathroom on Furqat Street. The restaurant "Dilshod", the building of the book house and the building of the large-format movie theater also give the city a unique look. The city is green and full of flowers. In the 70s and 80s of the last century, several new avenues, recreation areas, flower gardens were built in cultural and recreational parks. Trade in the city began to develop further. New advanced methods of trade have been introduced into the turnover of goods, and great attention is being paid to service. A wonderful view opens up along the railway ring route from Kokand to Chust: mulberry trees brought from China, endless cotton fields, mountain ridges, on the banks of the Sokh River, which starts 450 m above, since ancient times. the landowners grew onions, alfalfa, grapes, figs, pomegranates, and apricots. Kokan is the last major city on the route of the "Golden Fergana Ring" railway and highway. Rafkan railway station located on the right bank of Syrdarya separates the city of Koqan from the starting point of the trip. After that, the train will take us through Tajikistan to Tashkent, the capital of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is possible to take a car from Kokan and pass through the Angren valley through Kamchik Davani, which was used by caravan routes in the past. Nowadays, this wide and convenient road is opened for car traffic through two mountain tunnels built in the years of independence. It is also possible to go to Jizzakh and travel along the Great Silk Road to Samarkand through the Great Uzbek Tract. The history, monuments and architectural monuments of the cities of the Fergana Valley mentioned above are a resource for the development of tourist destinations. 29 Currently, foreign tourists are very interested in Margilon khan satin, Rishton ceramics and their creation process. In many destinations, tourists are directly involved in the creation of these items. In Appendix 1, several tourist destinations along the Golden Ring of Fergana are presented as examples.

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